

Introduction

*Sociology is interested only in the waking man
as if the sleeping man were a dead man
(Bastide 1972: 44)*

Dreaming Studies and the Social Sciences «out of Africa»

Between the biological and the social, the individual and the collective, the dream—understood as the psychic activity that unfolds during sleep—has constantly interrogated and fascinated humanity since antiquity. If the earliest treatises on dreams are found in the library of King Ashurbanipal in Mesopotamia (Mouton 2007), soon various philosophical schools (Pythagoreanism, Stoicism, Neoplatonism) and medical traditions (with the contributions of Hippocrates and Galen) would valorise the dream experience. Artemidorus's famous *Oneirokritika*, translated into Arabic in the third century, contributed to forging what Amira Mittermaier terms one of the greatest cultures of the dream (Mittermaier 2011). Aristotelian philosophy had a significant influence in the Middle Ages: in the *De somniis* Aristotle develops a theory of dreams that is predominantly physiological and psychological, rejecting strongly divinatory interpretations.

A desacralization of dreams began: they became less prophetic and started to individualize along singular paths (Le Goff 1999; Schmitt 2003), from the beginning of the eleventh century. Philosophers who have engaged with dreams are moreover numerous (Réné Descartes, Alfred Schutz or William James). Poets and writers have chronicled their dreams and even posited them as the foundation of poetic creation (Dragani 2017). Throughout history, certain intellectual and artistic movements, such as the Romanticism (e. g. Novalis with *Hymns to the Night*, Byron with *The Dream*) and the Surrealism have pivoted on the dream: for instance, André Breton in *The Manifesto of Surrealism* (1924) considers the dream a primary source of artistic inspiration. Poetry draws sustenance from states akin to dreaming (such as daydreaming and hypnosis) to conjure an otherworldly realm: for this reason, works like Paul Éluard's *Les Mains Libres* (1937) draw direct inspiration from dream visions.

A number of dream-banks have been produced spontaneously by individual dreamers over the centuries (from writers such as Franz Kafka and Marguerite Yourcenar to imprisoned members of the Red Brigades¹) as well as curated collections by scientists and intellectuals for research purposes, such as the DreamBank project, which aggregates over 22,000 catalogued dreams compiled by the American researchers Adam Schneider and G. William Domhoff.

¹ Valentino, N. 2011. *I sogni di Palmi. Raccolta di sogni dei reclusi del carcere speciale di Palmi*. Rome: Sensibili alle foglie.

As for the social sciences, the dream—conceived as an expression of individual and intrapsychic processes, in line with the dominant view in Western societies—has consequently been neglected and relegated to the domains of psychology and psychoanalysis. Yet these disciplines have exerted considerable influence on specific anthropologists and schools of thought across historical periods.

Often critiquing their ethnocentrism, social scientists have engaged and clashed over the concepts and theories forged by psychoanalysis: Sigmund Freud's (1856–1939) Oedipus complex and notions of libido, repression, and manifest/latent content; Carl G. Jung's (1875–1961) collective unconscious; Jacques Lacan's (1901–1981) unconscious as language; or Alfred Adler's (1870–1937) inferiority complex. Beyond psychoanalysis, psychologists specializing in dream analysis—beginning with pioneers of quantitative methods such as Mary Whiton Calkins, author of *Statistics of Dreams* (1893); the behavioural psychologist Calvin S. Hall (1909–1985) with his cognitive theory of dreaming in *The Content Analysis of Dreams* (Hall and Van de Castle 1966); Juliette M. Mageo (2003); or, more recently, neuroscientists (Hobson 1988; Foulkes 1999)—have likewise shaped research on dream life.

Although few social scientists have published articles or books specifically dedicated to oneirism, those who have tend to focus on dream practices and uses across different cultures, societies, groups, or social categories (sharing, circulation, interpretation) rather than on the meaning of dreams and their fabrication—leaving such speculations to psychologists and psychoanalysts, in a kind of scientific division of labour.

Within sociology, Roger Bastide (1950; 1967; 1972), Maurice Halbwachs (1877–1945), and more recently Fine, Fischer Leighton, and Bertrand Lahire (2018; 2021) (Bastide 1950, 1967, 1972; Duvignaud and Corbeau 1979; Halbwachs 1946; Fine and Fischer Leighton 1993) have laid the foundations for a sociology of dreams.

Historians as well have begun to interrogate dreams, contributing to a «social history of dreams» (Burke 1973). Dreams were collected in Nazi Germany during the Third Reich before the outbreak of World War II (Beradt 1985), among Vietnam veterans (Wilmer 2001), and in colonial Africa (Baum 2004; Cooper in this volume; Earle 2017; Mbembe 1991). Beyond research on dreams' interpretation and dream-sharing in diverse historical epochs, recent studies reflect on dream temporalities (Dragani 2018a; Fortier in this volume), disclosing how dreams are not only employed precognitively to predict the future (e.g., Jackson 1978; Basso 1987; Hollan 1989) but also to interpret the past and the occult—for instance, uncovering through a revelatory dream the malevolent actions and despicable individuals at the root of the afflictions tormenting the dreamer.

Anthropology has produced synthetic articles, edited volumes, and special issues—often in a comparative vein—on dreams (Mageo and Sheriff 2021; Poirier 1994; Caillois and Von Grunebaum 1967; Kennedy and Langness 1981; Spaulding 1981; Tedlock 1987; Lohmann 2003, among others).

Anthropologists have engaged with this theme since Edward B. Tylor (1832–1917), who considered the dream the origin of religion. On the question of “primitive” people's ability to distinguish between dream and reality rests the intellectual dispute that pitted Herbert Spencer (1820–1903) against Lucien Lévy-Bruhl (1857–1939).

In the United Kingdom, the links between anthropology and psychology were expressed in the works of William H. Rivers (1864–1922), such as *Dreams and Primitive Culture: A Lecture* (1918) and the book *Conflict and Dream* (1923), on the impact of war on dreams, in collaboration with C.

G. Seligman (1873–1940), who like Rivers had a medical background and treated shell shock among officers of the First World War. While appreciating Freud’s distinction between manifest and latent content, Seligman did not believe that dreams were solely expressions of unconscious desires, as in Freudian theory, but that they were linked to the instinct of self-preservation and to emotions such as fear and anger. Seligman encouraged his students to collect dreams in the field, but little was published on the topic, as they gradually adhered to the structural-functionalist paradigm, which was less inclined to probe the “individual” dimension of dreaming.

In the United States, psychological anthropology developed through the *Culture and Personality* school founded by Abraham Kardiner (1891–1981) and Cora Alice Du Bois (1903–1991), which was much more open to research on the impact of culture on dreams.

In general, the structuralist approach of the 1960s–1970s, centered on the analysis of dreams and their symbolism, produced quantitatively modest results, despite some interesting work such as Adam Kuper’s attempt to adapt structuralist methods of myth interpretation to dreams (1979), Lucien Sebag’s (1934–1965) analysis of the dreams of Baipurangi, a Guayaki woman (1964), or Philippe Descola’s studies among the Jívaro of Amazonia (1989).

From the 1980s onward, research reoriented toward an ethno-psychological approach, in Robin Sheriff’s sense (Mageo and Sheriff 2021: 30), through studies seeking to understand the local meanings of dreams and various aspects of dream practices, such as contextualization, socialization, enunciation, and the “performance” of dreams. The work of Dorothy Eggan (1901–1965) on the Hopi (1952) and of Barbara H. Tedlock (1942–2023) remains highly influential, with her studies contributing to what she called a “new anthropology of dreaming,” centred on practice (1987, 1991a).

Although research on dreams and visions has been particularly prolific in the Americas (Devereux 1957; Tedlock 1991b; Perrin 1992) and in Oceania (Lohmann 2003; Leblic 2010), the oneiric dimension has also been explored in Europe (Puccio 1996; Stewart 2017) and in Asia (Firth 1934; Stepanoff 2017), to name only a few examples. But what of Africa?

African studies and dreaming

Dreaming is a fascinating yet severely underdeveloped area of inquiry within African studies, in the sense that broad-ranging works—such as monographs or special issues—on this topic remain rare. The collection of oneiric material and the systematic study of dreams are still far from being mainstream objects in African-focused research.

C. G. Seligman is one of the pioneers in the study of dreams in an African context. Together with his wife Brenda Zara Salaman (1883–1965), he examined, on the one hand, the interpretation of prophetic dreams in south-western Sudan among the Lango and the Didinga (Seligman 1923). He also instructed his direct students to collect dreams in African settings, but this work—often preserved only in field notes housed in archives such as that of the London School of Economics—is rarely consolidated into authoritative publications. For example, Meyer Fortes (1906–1983) conducted fieldwork in Ghana between 1934 and 1937 and, together with his wife Sonia Donen,

recorded dreams related to divination or to the interpretation of oneiric signs in order to resolve social or ritual tensions (1959).

Edward E. Evans-Pritchard (1902–1973) contributes only marginally to the study of dreams among the Azande (southern Sudan). In *Witchcraft, Oracles and Magic among the Azande* (1937), dreams function as an ordinary medium of divination: the Azande interpret them as communications from the spirits of ancestors or from *mbisimo* (witchcraft). Sporadic references also appear in his studies of the Nuer (1940), where prophetic dreams are reported to guide pastoral migrations.

Siegfried F. Nadel (1903–1956) examines men's dreams among the Nupe in relation to divination (1954), and Farnham M. Rehfisch (1922–1990) reports a case of apparent death among the Mambilla in which a dying woman perceives herself as waking from a dream rather than from death (1969). Audrey Richards (1899–1984), in *Chisungu* (1956), documents dreams within initiation rituals for Bemba women (Zambia), where prophetic and premonitory dreams are said to guide the selection of candidates.

If interest in dreams in African contexts appears limited in the United Kingdom, the United States and to a lesser extent colonial France (Bondaz 2022) have produced a number of notable « ethnicist » studies on African populations such as the Hausa (Miles 1993; LeVine, Strangman, and Unterburger 1966; LeVine 1981; Shweder and LeVine 1975), the Uduk (James 1988), the Bambara (Bacou 1944) and the Zulu (Chidester 2008). Research was predicted also on more general or « national » relation to dreams with contributions related to dreaming in colonial Senegal (Bohumil 1946; 1949) and Guinea (Appia 1940).

Research on dreaming in religious settings is the most developed strand (Jedrej and Shaw 1992), where dreams can both challenge and reinforce a given religious system. Within Islamic contexts, several works focus on dreams and visions (Edgar 2011; Green 2015; Lamoureux 2002; Mittermaier 2011; Ogunnaike 2024; Pandolfo 2018). Other studies explore conversion dreams (Fischer 1979; Dragani 2026). In Christianity, dreams are also significant, especially in African contexts where dream-sharing in churches is studied as a practice that strengthens social cohesion (Charsley 1987; Droll 2023a; Droll 2023 b; Nell 2012). Moreover, dreams can be linked to materiality, as in Renne (2004), who shows how dreams and visions of angels in churches of south-western Nigeria appeared in garments, whose images were later transformed by tailors into clothing worn by church leaders.

More recently, research lines focus on “inspirational dreams” connected to artistic creation (Dilley 1992; Dragani 2016), “visitation dreams” tied to the world of the dead (Crapanzano 1975), and in relation to contemporary media technologies' influence on dreaming “television dreams” (Pype 2011; Mittermaier 2011) and « cinema dreams », for example in Nollywood (Droll 2022). An additional important strand highlights the political dimension of dream-sharing among migrants (Balzani 2010; Eneborg 2013) and refugees (Schubert and Punamäki 2016), where oneiric narratives are mobilized to negotiate belonging, trauma, and collective futures.

Philosophers and psychologists originating from the African continent are also writing on dreams, challenging the individualistic understanding of dreaming dominant in Western cultures. For these authors, in African contexts dreaming is often relational and communal—people dream for others and in relation to ancestors (Bynum 2021; Lajul 2024; Nyabul 2025; Nwoye 2017; Umezurike 2019; Uzoka 1988; Samb 1998; Saw 2008, 2009). The eminent anthropologist Joseph Tonda (2021)

develops the notion of the "dream of the Other" to conceptualize colonial, imperial, and capitalist domination, linking this concept to night-dreams, fantasies, and daydreams.

Dreaming in African Worlds and Words

This special issue seeks to investigate dreaming in Africa from a comparative and multidisciplinary perspective, through anthropological, historical, religious and literary approaches. It provides a venue for a deeper investigation into an existing research topic - though somewhat neglected in recent years - African dreaming, and to expand on this research, ethnographically and theoretically.

It attempts not only to describe oneiric material gathered in different African countries (Congo, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Mauritania and Senegal), languages, religions and epochs, but also to consider local attitudes towards night, sleep and oneirism. Through a comprehensive understanding of dreams in various contexts, dream studies enrich our knowledge of African imaginaries and their intersections with culture, religion, agency, and identity.

Barbara Cooper's essay focuses on students from across Colonial French West Africa who attended the famous William Ponty school in Senegal. They wrote essays in French on a host of topics presented to them by their teachers. In 1945 the boys were asked to write a lengthy essay on dreams during their vacations. In her paper Cooper discusses the responses of three students from Niger, each of whom came from regions in which multiple modes of Islamic dream interpretation co-existed with other ways of thinking about dreams in the light of the ubiquity of spirits of various kinds in the lives of their communities. Ethnically Cadot, Fulani and Hausa, the students provide glimpses of a variety of different settings.

Among the students discussed, Soumana Gouro presents dreaming as a delicate topic, because it involves multiple interpretations and cannot be reduced to a single explanation. He suggests that marabouts, spirit specialists and ordinary people all understand dreams differently, which makes dream interpretation both uncertain and contested. Another student, Mossi Adamou, is more sceptical and emphasizes that dreams are not considered central to decision-making, especially because professional interpreters can be exploitative. The third student, Koke Issaka, by contrast, uses dreams to reflect on colonial politics, presenting dream interpretation as a subtle way of commenting on French administrative power. In his account, a marabout interprets a dream about hyenas as referring to the French, turning the dream into a coded critique of colonial intervention.

Across the three accounts, dreams appear as a field where religion, politics and everyday life constantly overlap. The current collection of essays also stresses that dreams are often used for healing, divination and guidance, especially when people are trying to understand illness, uncertainty or social tension.

The article of Barbara Carbon draws on her fieldwork experience in Congo, and especially in Inga, where men dominate the spaces inside the hydro-electric complex and its administrative offices. But Inga is also peopled by women, who mostly remain in and near Inga's domestic realm. These women spend most of their time indoors, either at home or in church. They divide their time at home between watching TV, conducting household tasks, looking after the children or building their

own business. In Camp Kinshasa, women have a different kind of socio-economic freedom and responsibility and spend much of their time outdoors, collecting water, working the fields and selling fish or other goods at the market. Many women are educated and capable, but the remoteness of Inga limits their opportunities. Because of this, they spend long periods waiting for romantic, professional or economic change. During this “waithood”, daydreams and night-time dreams become important spaces of hope and planning. [Carbon understands daydreaming not simply as a personal cognitive habit, but as a culturally moulded mode of fantasy and collective significance. She examines how women are socialized into daydreaming, considered not just escapism but a mode of speculative agency, inventiveness, and a rehearsal for possible futures as for the unemployed young men in Ivory Coast described by Sasha Newell \(2012\).](#) Alongside, women use night dreams to turn vague desires into concise aspirations. Night dreams are often interpreted spiritually, especially as messages from God. These dreams can guide decisions about marriage, work, travel or family life. Women also share dreams with older married women or pastors, who help interpret them. This interpretation can influence reputation, relationships and future choices. Connections with men are often used strategically to improve economic security. At the same time such relationships can expose women to gossip and criticism.

In her article Corinne Fortier underlines that dreams in Islam and in Mauritanian Moorish society are deeply significant as they are considered a legitimate Islamic way of contacting the dead, especially deceased relatives, and of seeking guidance through divination. In Moorish society, dream interpretation is not seen as “occult” knowledge in a Western sense, but as a respected and orthodox part of Islamic religious tradition. The dead are thought to be close to God and able to intercede for the living. Visits to graves, and dreams of deceased relatives are therefore meaningful signs of blessing, piety or destiny.

Dreams often function as a form of incubation, where the soul of the dead enters the sleeper’s body and communicates with the living. This exchange is reciprocal: the dead may receive prayers, or help towards salvation, while the living receive advice, warnings or healing. Mauritanian marabouts can use *istikhāra*, a dream-based divinatory practice, not only for themselves but also for others who consult them. Through dreams they may learn about both past causes of suffering and future remedies, including magic or protective religious practices.

However, through ethnographic vignettes, Fortier illustrates how women in Mauritanian Moorish society contact the world of the dead through the medium of dreams. Women are especially associated with this contact with A striking feature of the communication is that it is often auditory rather than visual: hearing is considered more important than sight. In Mauritanian belief, the dead may not appear mainly as images, but as voices that speak within dreams.

Unlike a Western psychological view of dreams, this tradition treats dreams as extending the person and family beyond death. As a result, dream life in Mauritania preserves kinship, religious authority and ongoing dialogue across the boundary between life and death.

Rare works have been consecrated to dreaming in literary studies (Chimombo 2009; Constant 2008). In his paper, Dikko Muhammad tackles the dream motif in the literary output of Northern Nigerian writers. However, despite its manifestations in many of these authors, the phenomenon of dream in these vast works has not been explicitly studied. This paper explores the representations of dreams in the literary spaces of Northern Nigeria. It locates the characters’ attempts to situate their fears and desires within the dominant Islamic ideologies and the manifestation of these desires, spirituality, and fears in their dreams. Dream does not just portray the characters’ desires, fears, and

expectations but also the unseen through the prism of the dominant ideology – Islam. The representations portray the influence of Islam and Islamic practices that go beyond the conscious world into the world of sleep. Relationships and crises are negotiated and addressed through exchanges in the dream world. Dreams often serve as a link that connects the living and the dead, and characters continue to relate to and take guidance from their loved ones who have departed to the world of the dead. This form of relationship evinces a philosophical influence on the concept of dream and its presence in religiosity. The dream casts light on the religious stature of the dreamers – a status that enables a divine guide into their lives through dreams. In this form of literary dialogue, the world of the dead and the living are brought together seamlessly.

Eclectic and regardless to theoretical perspectives, this special section focuses on various dimensions of African dream accounts as they are influenced by language, history, religious factors, gender attitudes and cultural frameworks. The present issue is made up of an interdisciplinary, intergenerational and international group of scholars from inside and outside Africa. Africa. By a multidisciplinary approach, its expressed intention is to bridge the gap between publications on dreaming specializing only onto anthropology on the one hand, and other academic disciplines on the other (history, literary and visual studies), representing a range of intellectual interests.

Bibliography

Appia, B. 1940. “Superstitions guinéennes et sénégalaises.” *Bulletin de l'IFAN* 2: 358-396.

Bacou, P. 1944. “Quelques interprétations de rêves chez les Bambaras de Doumba (Subdivision de Koulikoro).” *Notes africaines* 22: 11-21.

Balzani, M. 2010. “Dreaming, Islam and the Ahmadiyya Muslims in the UK.” *History and Anthropology* 21(3): 293–305.

Baum, R. M. 2004. “Crimes of the Dream World: French Trials of Diola Witches in Colonial Senegal.” *The International Journal of African Historical Studies* 37(2): 210–228.

Bastide, R. 1950. “Rêves de Noirs.” *Psyché* 49 : 802-811.

Bastide, R. 1967. “Sociologie du Rêve.” In R. Caillois et G.E. von Grunebaum (dir.), *Le rêve et les sociétés humaines*, Paris, Gallimard : 177-188.

Bastide, Roger. 1972. *Le Rêve, la transe et la folie*. Paris: Flammarion.

Basso E. B., 1987. “The Implications of a Progressive Theory of Dreaming.” 86-104, in B. Tedlock (dir.) *Dreaming. Anthropological and Psychological Interpretations*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Beradt, C. 1985. *The Third Reich of Dreams: The Nightmares of a Nation, 1933–1939*. Wellingborough: Aquarian Press.

Bondaz, J. 2022. “L’onirotèque de l’IFAN. Collecter les rêves à la fin de la période coloniale.” *Troubles dans les collections* 3 online. <https://troublesdanslescollections.fr/numeros/linstitut-fictionnel-dafrique-noire/lonirotheque-de-lifan/>

Burke, Peter. 1973. “Histoire sociale des rêves.” *Annales. Économies, Sociétés, Civilisations* 28 (2): 329–342.

Bynum, E. B., 2021. “The African origin of familial consciousness and the dynamics of dreaming.” *Dreaming* 31 (2): 91 - 99.

Caillois, Roger and Gustav E. von Grunebaum (eds). 1967. *Les rêves et les sociétés humaines*. Paris: Éditions Gallimard.

Calkins M. W., 1893. “Statistics of dreams.” *American Journal of Psychology* 5 (3) : 311-343.

Charsley, S. R. 1973. “Dreams in an African Independent Church.” *Africa* 43 (3) : 244–257.

Chidester, D. 2008. “Dreaming in the Contact Zone: Zulu Dreams, Visions, and Religion in Nineteenth-Century South Africa.” *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* 76 (1) : 27–53.

Chimombo, Stanlake S. J. 1989. “Dreams and Ntara’s Man of Africa.” *Journal of African Religion in Africa* 19: 48–70.

Constant, I. 2008. *Le rêve dans le roman africain et antillais*. Paris: Karthala Éditions.

Crapanzano, V. 1975. “Saints, jnun and dreams: An Essay in Moroccan Ethnopsychology.” *Psychiatry* 38 (2) : 145–159.

Curley, R. T. 1992. “Private Dreams and Public Knowledge in a Camerounian Independent Church.” in *Dreaming, Religion and Society in Africa*, ed. M.C. Jędrej and Rosalind Shaw (Leiden: Brill, 1992), 139.

Devereux, G. 1957. “Dream Learning and Individual Ritual Differences in Mohave Shamanism.” *American Anthropologist* 59 (6) : 1036–1045.

Descola, P. 1989. “Head-Shrinkers versus Shrinks: Jivaroan Dream Analysis.” *Man* 24: 439–450.

Dilley, R. M. 1992. “Dreams, Inspiration and Craftwork among Tukolor Weavers.” In M. C. Jędrej and R. Shaw (dir.). *Dreaming, Religion and Society in Africa*. Leiden: Brill, p. 71–85.

Dragani, A. 2012. *Interno tuareg. Etnografia dei poeti nomadi del Niger*. Rome: Aracne.

Dragani, A. 2013. “Biographies de poètes : sang, maladie et rêve.” in *Poésie des gens du désert*, Tamanrasset: Dar Al Imzad: 85- 98.

- Dragani, A. 2016. “ Rêve, sang et maladie. Biographies nocturnes et diurnes de poètes touaregs. ” *Journal des Africanistes* 85(1-2): 358–375.
- Dragani, A. 2017. “Vers une anthropologie de la créativité poétique.” in A. Dragani et D. Casajus (dir.). *Le poète et l'inspiration*. In *Cahiers de littérature orale* 81: 10-13.
- Dragani, A. 2018a. “The Past of Dreams: Gender, Memory and Tuareg Oneiric Inspiration.” *Africa* 88(1): 122–137. doi:10.1017/S0001972017000596
- Dragani, A. 2018b. “Le genre du rêve. Pratiques oniriques et oniromantiques chez les Touaregs.” *Anthropologie et sociétés* 42 (2-3) : 361–383
- Dragani A. 2026. “ Saharan Conversion from Islam to Christianity. A View from Mali and Niger.” in A. Adhlakun (ed.). *Brill Encyclopedia of Global Pentecostalism Supplements*. Leyde: Brill (to be print).
- Droll, A. 2022. “Dreams, Visions, and the African Melodrama: A Commentary on the Interface Between Cinematography and Pentecostal Epistemology.” *PentecoStudies* 21(1): 51-72.
- Droll, Anna M. Pentecostal Principle and the Dreams and Visions of African Visionaries. In *Public Righteousness: The Performative Ethics of Human Flourishing*. Adhlakun, Abimbola A., Ed. Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2023.
- Droll, A. 2023b. *Dreams and Visions in African Pentecostal Spirituality: The Sub-Saharan Horizon of the Pneumatological Imagination*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill Publishers.
- Duvignaud Jean, Françoise Duvignaud and Jean-Pierre Corbeau J. P. 1979. *La Banque des rêves. Essai d'anthropologie du rêver contemporain*. Paris: Payot.
- Earle, J. 2017. “ Dreams and Political Imagination in Colonial Buganda.” *Journal of African History* 58 (1) : 85–105.
- Edgar, I. R. 2011. *The Dream in Islam: From Qur'anic Tradition to Jihadist Inspiration*. New York: Berghahn Books.
- Eggan, D. 1952. “The Manifest Content of Dreams: A Challenge to Social Science.” *American Anthropologist* 54 (2) : 469–485.
- Eneborg, Y. M. 2013. “Ruqya Shariya: Observing the Rise of a New Faith Healing Tradition amongst Muslims in East London.” *Mental Health, Religion & Culture* 16 (10) : 1080–1096.
- Evans-Prichard E. E. 1937. *Witchcraft, Oracles and Magic Among the Azande*, Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Evans-Prichard E. E. 1940. *The Nuer: A Description of the Modes of Livelihood and Political Institutions of a Nilotic people* London: Clarendon Press.
- Nelson Osamu Hayashida. 1999. *Dreams in the African Church: The Significance of Dreams and Visions Amongst African Baptists*. Atlanta, GA: Rodopi.

Özgen Felek and Alexander D. Knysh (eds.). 2012. *Dreams and Visions in Islamic Societies*. Alban : State University of New York Press.

Hélas, B. 1946. "Quelques recettes employées au Sénégal pour provoquer les rêves." *Notes africaines* 32: 8-9.

Holas, B. 1949. "La clé des songes des musulmans sénégalais." *Notes africaines* 42 : 45-49.

Fabian, J. 1966. "Dream and Charisma: "Theories of Dreams" in the Jamaa Movement (Congo)." *Anthropos* 61 (2) : 544-560.

Fine, G. A., Fisher Leighton L., 1993. "Nocturnal Omissions: Steps Towards a Sociology of Dreams." *Symbolic Interaction* 16 (12): 95-104.

Firth R., 1934. "The Meaning of Dreams in Tikopia." 63-74. In E. Evans-Prichard et alii (dir.), *Essays Presented to C.G. Seligman* Londres: Kegan Paul.

Fisher, H. 1979. "Dreams and Conversion in Black Africa." In N. Levtzion (dir.) 217-235. *Conversion to Islam*. New York: Holmes and Meier.

Freud, S. 1938. *The Interpretation of Dreams*. In A. A. Brill (éd.), *The Basic Writings of Sigmund Freud*. New York: Random House.

Foulkes, 1999. D. *Children's Dreaming and the Development of Consciousness*. Cambridge MA-London: Harvard University Press.

Green, N. 2015. "A Brief World History of Muslim Dreams," *Islamic Studies* 54 (3-4) : 143-167.

Hall, C. S. and R. L. Van de Castle. 1966. *The Content Analysis of Dreams*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.

Groak, K. 2019. "Freud among the Boasians: Psychoanalytic Influence and Ambivalence in American Anthropology." *Current Anthropology* 60 (04) : 559-588.

Halbwachs M. 1946. "Le rêve et le langage inconscient dans le sommeil." *Journal de psychologie normale et pathologique* 39 : 11- 64

Hollan, D. 1989. "The Personal Use of Dream Beliefs in the Toraja Highlands.» *Ethos* 17 (2) : 166-186.

Hobson, J. A. 1988. *The Dreaming Brain*. New York: Basic Books.

Hollan, D. 1995. "To the Afterworld and Back: Mourning and Dreams of the Dead among the Toraja." *Ethos* 23 (4): 424-36.

Jackson, M. 1978. "An Approach to Kuranko Divination" *Human Relations* 31:117-138.

James, W. 1988. *The Listening Ebony: Moral Knowledge, Religion and Power among the Uduk of Sudan*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.

- Jedrej, M. C. Et R. Shaw (dir.). 1992. *Dreaming, Religion and Society in Africa*. Leiden: Brill.
- Kennedy, J. G. and L. L. Langness (dir.). 1981. *Dreams Ethos* 9 (4).
- Kuper, A. 1979. "A Structural Approach to Dreams" *Man* 14(4): 645–662.
- Lamoreaux, J. C. 2002. *The Early Muslim Tradition of Dream Interpretation*. Albany (NY): State University of New York Press.
- Lajul, W. 2024. "Pre-scientific and scientific theories of human dream: an African philosophical perspective." *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review* 07 (03) : 134-144.
- Leblic, I. 2010. "Les Kanak et les rêves, ou comment redécouvrir ce que les ancêtres n'ont pas transmis (Nouvelle-Calédonie) ». *Journal de la Société des Océanistes* 130: 105–118.
- Le Goff, J. 1999. "Le Christianisme et les rêves: Ile–VIIe siècles ». In *Un autre Moyen Âge*. Paris, Gallimard: 689–740.
- LeVine, Robert A., Eugene Strangman, E. and Leonard Unterberger, L. 1966. *Dreams and Deeds: Achievement Motivation in Nigeria*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- LeVine, S. 1981. "Dreams of the Informant about the Researcher: Some Difficulties Inherent in the Research Relationship". *Ethos* 9 (4) : 276–293.
- Lowie, R. 1966. "Dreams, idle Dreams." *Current Anthropology* 7 (3) : 378-382.
- Lohmann, R. (dir.). 2003. *Dream Travelers: Sleep Experiences and Culture in the Western Pacific*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mageo, J., 2003 *Dreaming and the Self: New Perspectives on Subjectivity, Identity, and Emotion*, Albany, NY: State University of New York Press.
- Mageo J., Sheriff R., 2021. *New Directions in the Anthropology of Dreams*. London: Routledge.
- Mbembe, A. 1991. " Domaines de la Nuit et Autorité Onirique dans les Maquis du Sud-Cameroun (1955–1958)." *Journal of African History* 32(1): 89–121.
- Miles, W. 1993. " Hausa Dreams." *Anthropologica* 35: 105–106.
- Mittermaier, A. 2011. *Dreams That Matter: Egyptian Landscapes of the Imagination*. Berkeley / Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- Mouton, A. 2007. *Rêves hittites. Contribution à une histoire et une anthropologie du rêve en Anatolie ancienne*. Leyde-Boston: Brill.
- Nadel, F. 1954. *Nupe Religion*. London: Rutledge.
- [Nell, W. 2012. "Religion and spirituality in contemporary dreams." *Theological Studies* 68 \(1\) : 101-109.](#)

Newell, S., 2012. *The Modernity Bluff: Crime, Consumption, and Citizenship in Côte d'Ivoire*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.

Nwoye, A. 2017. "The Psychology and Content of Dreaming in Africa". *Journal of Black Psychology*. " 43(1): 3–26.

Nyabul, P. O. 2025. "The significance of dreams and dreaming in the traditional culture of Luo people in Kenya. *Dreaming* 35 (4): 311-320.

Ogunnaike, O. 2024. "Dreaming Sufism in the Sokoto Caliphate: Dreams and Knowledge in the Works of Shaykh Dan Tafa." *Intellectual History of the Islamic World*, 12(3):179-212. <https://doi.org/10.1163/2212943x-bja10013>

Pandolfo, S. 2018. *Knot of the Soul. Madness, Psychoanalysis, Islam*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.

Perrin, M. 2001. *Les praticiens du rêve. Un exemple de chamanisme*. Paris: Presses universitaires de France.

Poirier, S. 1994 (ed.). *Rêver la culture*. In *Anthropologie et Société* 18(2) : 5–11.

Puccio, D. 1996. "Les rêves de Teresa." *Terrain* 26: 19–36.

Pype, K. 2011. " Dreaming the Apocalypse: Mimesis and the Pentecostal Imagination in Kinshasa." *Paideuma* 11: 81–96.

Richards, A., 1956. *Chisungu: A Girl's Initiation Ceremony among the Bemba of Zambia* London: Faber and Faber.

Rehfishch, F. 1969. " Death, Dreams and the Ancestors and Mambila Culture." In M. Douglas et P. M. Kaberry (dir.) *Man in Africa*. London: Tavistock Press: 307–315.

Rivers, W. H. R. 1918. *Dreams and Primitive Culture: A Lecture*, Whitefish MT : Kessinger Publishing's Rare reprints.

Rivers, W. H. R. 1923. *Conflict and Dreams*, Kessinger Publishing's Rare reprints: Whitefish MT.

Renne, E. P. 2004. " Dressing in the Stuff of Dreams: Sacred Dress and Religious Authority in Southwestern Nigeria." *Dreaming* 14 (2–3) : 120–135. doi:10.1037/1053-0797.14.2-3.120.

Seligman, C. G. 1923. " Note on Dreams." *Man* 23: 186–188. doi:10.2307/2788568.

Schubert, C. C. & R-L. Punamäki. 2016. "Posttraumatic Nightmares of Traumatized Refugees: Dream Work Integrating Cultural Values." *Dreaming* 26 (1): 10–28. doi:10.1037/drm0000021.

Schmitt, J.-C. 2003. " Récits et images de rêves au Moyen Âge." *Ethnologie française* 33 (4) : 553–563.

- Sebag, L. 1964. "Analyse des rêves d'une Indienne guayaki." *Les Temps modernes* 217: 2181–2237.
- Shweder, Richard and Robert A. LeVine. 1975. "Dream Concepts of Hausa Children: A Critique of the Doctrine of Invariant Sequence in Cognitive Development." *Ethos* 3 (2) : 209–230.
- Samb, D. 1998. *L'interprétation des rêves dans la région sénégalaise, suivi de La clef des songes de la Sénégambie, de l'Égypte pharaonique et de la tradition islamique*. Dakar: Nouvelles Éditions Africaines du Sénégal.
- Sow, I. 2008. *La symbolique de l'imaginaire. Dialectique du faste et du néfaste à partir des pré-sages, superstitions et gaaf*. Dakar: IFAN-CAD.
- Sow, I. 2009. *Divination, marabout, destin. Aux sources de l'imaginaire*, Dakar: IFAN-CAD.
- Spaulding, J. 1981. "The dream in other cultures. Anthropological studies of dreams and dreaming." *Dreamworks* 1 (4) 1981: 330-342.
- Stepanoff C. 2017. "La tente sombre ou l'antichambre du rêve." *Annuaire de l'École pratique des hautes études, Section des sciences religieuses* 124:15-18.
- Stewart, C. 2017. *Dreaming and Historical Consciousness in Island Greece*, Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Tedlock, B. (dir.). 1987. *Dreaming: Anthropological and Psychological Interpretations*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Tedlock, B. 1991a. "The New Anthropology of Dreaming." *Dreaming*, 1 (2) : 161-178.
- Tedlock, B. 1991b. *The Way of the Shaman: Spiritual Journeys in the World of the Dream*. New York: Penguin Books.
- Tonda, J. 2021. *Afrodystopie. La vie dans le rêve d'Autrui*. Paris: Karthala.
- Uzoka, A. 1988. "Dreams and Behaviour: Attribution of Causation to Dreams in a Nigerian Population." *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology* 23: 60–63.
- Umezurike, G. 2019. "Understanding Dream and its Causes: European and African Continental Experience." *IDOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 4 (1) : 88–101.
- Wilmer, H. 2001. "The Healing Nightmare: War Dreams of Vietnam Veterans." In D. Barrett (dir.). *Trauma and Dreams*. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press.
- Whiton Calkins, M. 1893. "Statistics of Dreams." *The American Journal of Psychology* 5(3): 311–343. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1410996>